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**Religion, Region, Language and the State
ERC SYNERGY PROJECT ASIA 609823
Project workshops 2016-2017**

This document provides a record of the Project Workshops organised under the leadership of Dr Nathan Hill (SOAS) during project period 2 (months 19 – 36, March 2016 to August 2017). As a rule, workshops have been held monthly except in the summer break (July and August).

March 2016

The Ethos of Royalty in Gupta-Period Literature

Dr Csaba Dezső (Eötvös Loránd University)

Date: 8 March 2016 Time: 2:00 PM
Finishes: 8 March 2016 Time: 5:00 PM
Venue: 21/22 Russell Square Room: MBI Al Jaber Room

This talk examine passages selected from Gupta period literature, which deal with norms and values that determine the course of action a king might take in peace and war, and reflect what was considered to be achievable, what was a virtue and what was a vice, what was aesthetically pleasing and what was ugly. The text in the focus of the talk will be the *Raghuvamśa*, but I am also going to take examples from Buddhist literature. The relation of these texts to the *Arthaśāstra* will also be discussed.

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April 2016

Spatial Technologies for Research on Past Societies

Dr Riza Abbas (Indian Institute of Research in Numismatic Studies, Nasik), Dr Anne Casile (French Institute of Research for Development, Paris), Dr Jason Hawkes (British Museum), and Dr Michael Willis (British Museum)

Date: 12 April 2016 Time: 2:00 PM
Finishes: 12 April 2016 Time: 5:00 PM
Venue: 21/22 Russell Square Room: T102

Geographical Information Systems (GIS) offer a powerful set of tools for research on past societies and for the interpretation, display and management of spatial and thematic data. These can be obtained from a wide range of sources: material and

environmental records, archives, maps, landscapes, GPS readings, statistics, aerial photography, remote sensing imageries, web-mapping and much more.

This workshop will provide, firstly, an introduction to GIS and discuss the potential – and limitations – of using spatial technologies for archaeological and historical research. It will also call attention to issues of data dissemination using web-mapping and GIS-based interfaces. The second part of the workshop will look at the application of GIS to the study and understanding of developments in ancient Vidarbha. The types and scales of archaeological evidence in Vidarbha – and how this evidence can be managed and interpreted in a GIS framework – will form the basis for discussion and planning.

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May 2016

Epigraphy at Bodhgaya

Dr Dániel Balogh (British Museum), Dr Tilman Frasch (Manchester Metropolitan), Dr Gergely Hidas (British Museum) Dr Sam van Schaik (British Library), Dr Vincent Tournier (SOAS, University of London), and Dr Michael Willis (British Museum)

Date: 10 May 2016

Time: 2:00 PM

Finishes: 10 May 2016

Time: 5:00 PM

Venue: Russell Square: College Buildings

Room: L67

Bodhgaya, long recognized as the place where the Buddha gained enlightenment, has important archaeological, artistic and literary remains that bear witness to site's enduring significance over the last 2,300 years.

For this workshop, five researchers with interests in Bodhgaya will come together to lead a discussion of the Bodhgaya archive in the British Museum. The workshop will focus on three key inscriptions from the site that are documented in the archive: on the oldest Buddha image from the site (late 4th century CE), on the main Buddha image now installed in the temple (13th century CE), and a Burmese inscription recording the restoration of the temple (also of the 13th century). The 13th century material overlaps and intersects with the accounts of Tibetan travellers, a subject that will also be introduced. The second half of the workshop will focus on the reading of the 4th century inscription in view of its landmark importance and the need for an improved reading. Materials will be circulated ahead.

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June 2016

Kushan State Formation: From a Horse Breeders' Tribe to an Empire

Prof Harry Falk (Freie Universität Berlin)

Date: 14 June 2016

Time: 2:00 PM

Finishes: 14 June 2016
Venue: Russell Square: College Buildings

Time: 5:00 PM
Room: 116

The Yuezhi, as the Chinese chronicles call the Kushans, were expelled from Gansu in western China in ca. 206 BC, and driven out of an intermediate home 30 years later. After two expulsions and traveling almost 3000 km they ended up in Bactria. Starting as refugees they regained strength and widened their geographical basis within a century. Profiting from the opening of the Silk Road and controlling two of the most frequented inroads from the East they changed their administration from monarchy to federal states and back to monarchy. Their affluence led to comparisons with the other contemporaneous strong states, China, Iran and Rome. Royal habits and cultural achievements in those states also shaped the way the Kushans attempted to represent imperial greatness. Their state income was based on an exchange among a multitude of trading centers. The collapse of the empire went along with the collapse of those cities - or the other way round.

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July 2016 – No Workshop

August 2016 – No Workshop

September 2016

Digital Humanities

Dr Roger Evans (Brighton), Dr Stefan Baums (LMU Munich), and Stephen White (Venice)

Date: 13 September 2016
Finishes: 13 September 2016
Venue: Russell Square: College Buildings

Time: 2:00 PM
Time: 5:00 PM
Room: 22 RS T101

Text Mining Medieval Charters: Perspectives from Two Projects

Dr Roger Evans (University of Brighton)

This paper reports on two recent projects working with historians and archivists to unlock the potential of free text content in historical documents. The ChartEx project, led by Historians at York, developed a researcher's workbench to support the exploration of medieval charters. Traces through Time, led by The National Archive, extracted biographical and prosopographical information across almost 1000 years of historical record, from charters right up to the First World War, to support exploration of the archives through the individuals that inhabit them. My group's contribution to these projects was the 'deep' natural language processing components, and focused particularly on the earlier documents which contained more free text. The presentation will give an overview of the two projects as a whole, and explore their different perspectives on content extraction from charters, one event-based, the other person-based, and the as yet unrealised potential for combining the two into a single more comprehensive analysis of charter documents.

The Research Environment for Ancient Documents: Digital Editions, Paleography and EpiDoc Integration

Dr Stefan Baums (Bavarian Academy of Sciences and Humanities, Ludwig Maximilian University of Munich) and Stephen White (digital humanities software engineer, Venice)

The Research Environment for Ancient Documents (READ) is a new software system for the study of ancient texts and their physical carriers. It is designed to support editorial, paleographic and lexicographic work on documents from any part of the ancient world, with an initial focus on South Asian manuscripts and inscriptions. Core architectural features of READ are the close linking of images, transcriptions and analysis, and the ability to handle multiple interpretations of the same document in parallel, with applications for the history of research on documents and for concurrent collaborative work on them. READ is implemented as an interactive web interface on top of a relational database, with the possibility of networked and local installations. It uses a self-documenting XML schema for archival and backup purposes, and implements EpiDoc TEI for data exchange with other software and integration into established workflows. This presentation will start with a brief description of the source material and digital infrastructure that READ initially grew out of, supporting a network of scholars editing and studying early Buddhist manuscripts and related South Asian epigraphic corpora. It will then discuss the design process behind READ, intended to meet the needs of broader user communities, and its current set of features.

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October 2016

Recent Research on Pyu Language and Material Culture

Dr Marc Miyake (British Museum) and Prof Janice Stargardt (Cambridge)

Date: 11 October 2016	Time: 2:00 PM
Finishes: 11 October 2016	Time: 5:00 PM
Venue: Russell Square: College Buildings	Room: 22 RS T102

The Perils of Pyu: Roadblocks to Decipherment

Dr Marc Miyake (British Museum)

What is now upper Burma was once the realm of the Pyu civilization in the first millennium CE. The Pyu established city-states centuries before the arrival of Burmese speakers from the northwest. The newcomers conquered the Pyu who then gradually assimilated. Their written language lingered until the late 13th century before disappearing. The Pyu language was unread for over a half a millennium until Charles Otto Blagden's pioneering decipherment of the Pyu text of the 12th century Myazedi inscription in 1911. Although over a century has passed since then, progress in the understanding of Pyu has remained limited despite two huge advantages: (1) an identifiable affiliation with the Sino-Tibetan family and (2) an Indic script. In this talk I will explain why it is still so difficult to crack the Pyu code. The aforementioned advantages are not omnipotent keys. Linguistic relatives do not reveal many secrets,

and the devil is in the details of Pyu spelling. And those big pluses with caveats are outweighed by an even bigger minus: the paucity of multilingual material. How can I overcome this obstacle?

Two Seasons of Excavations at Sri Ksetra, Myanmar: the Cambridge–Field School of Archaeology Joint Project on Pyu Settlement Archaeology
Prof Janice Stargardt (Cambridge)

This lecture presents some of the results of the excavations carried out at Sri Ksetra for five months in 2015-2016. For the first time, archaeologists succeeded in identifying a Pyu habitation site and, in the first season exposed a long sequence of domestic activities dating from the mid-fifth to the late seventh century CE. This work also provided many materials for constructing the first typology and chronology of Pyu ceramics in that period. When work resumed late in 2015, however, some surprises were in store. The decayed traces of ancient wooden floors and postholes were found, scattered over an area of 1.5 ha., proving beyond doubt that this was the remains of an ancient community, living in wooden houses built on wooden pillars near the Yahanda gate of Sri Ksetra. Just above the floors were found the sherds of well-formed ceramics decorated in Indic techniques - rouletting and stamping - and bearing motifs sacred to both Hinduism and Buddhism. Below the floors of four houses, still greater surprises awaited: cremated human remains buried in ceramic urns. Under one house no fewer than twelve such burials were found, representing a long funerary sequence in three geological layers without offerings, but carefully installed in compacted earth and defined by brick alignments. Clearly, in Pyu culture the living chose to dwell close to the dead.

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November 2016

Tax Exemptions, Religious Codes, and Equality before the Law: Jostling for Fiscal Privilege among Buddhist and Brahminical Ascetics in Ancient India
Dr Ulrich Pagel (SOAS, University of London)

Date: 8 November 2016	Time: 2:00 PM
Finishes: 8 November 2016	Time: 5:00 PM
Venue: Russell Square: College Buildings	Room: 4426

This talk explores the Buddhist response towards duty demands encountered at the customs office as its monks crossed from one administrative area into another. The presentation will compare the tax obligations of the Sangha with those imposed on the members of the Hindu ascetic orders and charts the factors that shaped the evolving positions of privilege. For the Buddhist position, the talk will draw mainly on the monastic code of the Mūlasarvastivāda school which records the emerging tax disputes in great detail. The religious principles and cultural ideals that informed the tax obligations of the Hindu ascetics are set out in the Dharmaśāstra literature. Even though both traditions subscribe to similar soteriological aspirations, because they held different positions in society and state ideology, and enjoyed access to different

levels of property, Hindu ascetics were often privileged over their Buddhist peers in matters of taxation. Buddhist lawyers strove to overturn this 'injustice' invoking the authority of ancient Hindu treatises of governance. In the end, the prospect of lucrative tax returns from monastic treasuries, perhaps coupled with concern about the rise of Buddhist influence in the commercial sector, prevailed and silenced Buddhist protestations of discrimination and bias. Some monks resorted to tax evasion but most paid up, reluctantly.

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December 2016

Intoxicants in Gupta Period South Asia

Prof James McHugh (University of Southern California)

Date: 13 December 2016	Time: 2:00 PM
Finishes: 13 December 2016	Time: 5:00 PM
Venue: Russell Square: College Buildings	Room: 22 RS T102

In this paper I will present an account of the use of alcohol and betel in the Gupta period. There is a tendency to assume that the cultures of alcohol and betel consumption, as well as religious prohibitions, were somewhat timeless in South Asia. By contrast I wish to develop a more nuanced historical understanding for the Gupta period regarding the types of alcoholic drinks and betel preparations that were traded, consumed, and regulated. I shall examine the modes of consumption and types of restriction that are most prominent in texts from this period, comparing these representations of practice with both earlier and later ones in order to give a sense of what is distinctive about Gupta period drug use (in the broadest sense of the word "drug.") These drugs ranged from simple, local rice-beers to imported wines and exotically perfumed betel wraps, creating many opportunities for hierarchical display, distinction and exclusion. The picture that emerges is, of course, somewhat messy, and surviving representations are highly stylized, but despite this conventionality and inconsistency I will attempt to historicize both my textual sources, the practices, and drinks with reference to the greater religious, political, and cultural history of the period.

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January 2017

Strategies of Expansion: Evidence for the Spread of the Buddhist Image Cult at the Kānherī Caves

Prof Robert D. DeCaroli (George Mason University)

Date: 10 January 2017	Time: 2:00 PM
Finishes: 10 January 2017	Time: 5:00 PM
Venue: Brunei Gallery	Room: B211

Much has been written about the likely origins of the Buddhist image tradition in the regions of Mathura and Gandhāra, but little work has been done tracing the expansion of those practices into other parts of South Asia. By examining the early physical contexts into which these practices spread we can gain insights into mechanisms by which image use was integrated into extant Buddhist centers. This paper will explore the expansion of image-based practices into the Western Deccan with special attention given to the Kānherī caves. These artistic innovations will be shown to have taken place under the rule, if not the direct patronage, of the Sātavāhana rulers. This study reveals parallels between Buddhist developments in the Deccan and in the Mathurān heartland. In both cases the rise of image-centered devotion coincides with a contemporaneous emergence of royal portraiture and an expanded use of imagery in religious contexts. Therefore, the rise and development of the image cult in South Asian Buddhism must be understood as only one aspect of a larger societal and cultural shift towards the increased public use of figural imagery. Buddhist literary discussions of images and of the Buddha's bodily form may therefore be better understood as justifications of practices which find their inspiration in developments located partially, even primarily, outside the Buddhist tradition.

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February 2017

Early Buddhism and Central Asia

Dr Hannes A. Fellner (Vienna), Prof Jan Nattier (UC Berkeley), and Prof Jonathan Silk (Leiden)

Date: 14 February 2017	Time: 2:00 PM
Finishes: 14 February 2017	Time: 5:00 PM
Venue: Brunei Gallery	Room: B104

Tocharian Buddhism

Dr Hannes A. Fellner (University of Vienna)

Tocharian, an Indo-European language attested in two closely related varieties from the 4th-10th c. CE, was discovered in the early 1900s. Tocharian manuscripts hail from the city-states and oases of the Silk Road in the Tarim Basin (in today's Xinjiang, PRC). Almost all Tocharian manuscripts are Buddhist, translated or adapted from Sanskrit and Prakrit sources. While the canonical texts tend to reflect the Śrāvakayāna school, the non-canonical texts are influenced by Mahāyāna traditions.

This talk examines (1) Buddhist genres that thrived among the Tocharians and (2) Buddhist terminology in Tocharian.

(1) *Jātaka*, *avadāna* and *nāṭaka* texts enjoyed a popularity witnessed by their disproportionately high number among the surviving manuscripts. Tocharian exclusively preserves a number of texts of these genres lost in other traditions.

(2) Unlike other languages of Buddhism, e.g. Tibetan, there are no established equivalents between Indic and Tocharian terms. There are different layers of Buddhist terminology ranging from foreign words to loanwords, from calques to the use of

indigenous vocabulary, sometimes with marked differences between the two Tocharian languages. The different layers of adoption of terminology correlate with different waves of the Buddhist missions.

Finally, this talk addresses the role that Tocharian played in the transmission of Buddhism from India to China.

Transmission and Translation: Reassessing the role of Central Asia in the Formation of Chinese Buddhism

Prof Jan Nattier (University of California, Berkeley)

The early history of Chinese Buddhism is often described as the history of the translation of Buddhist texts. This is true not only of modern studies but of early medieval Chinese sources as well, which prominently feature the activity of translators. Ever since the publication of J. W. de Jong's seminal paper "Buddha's Word in China" (the 28th George Ernest Morrison Lecture, delivered in Canberra in 1968), scholars have been aware that in the initial period of the dissemination of Buddhism in China translators of Central Asian (rather than Indian) origin played a pivotal role.

Nearly fifty years later, in the wake of spectacular new manuscript finds and the availability of increasingly sophisticated studies of Chinese translations using digital texts, we are now in a position to reassess de Jong's contention that Central Asian translators played a key role in the formation of Chinese Buddhism. De Jong's general assessment will still hold, but using these new resources we can now view the situation from a variety of angles that were only faintly visible before.

How to access a native speaker's reading of Medieval Chinese: Tibetan translations of Chinese from Dunhuang

Prof Jonathan Silk (Leiden University)

Among the materials preserved in Dunhuang are several Tibetan translations of scriptures made not from Sanskrit Indian sources but from Chinese. Among other things, these precious materials allow us access to contemporary educated readings of Chinese sources. This presentation introduces these materials and explores some aspects of their value.

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March 2017

An 'Arm of the Earth', an 'Eagle Banner', and a 'Spear of Dharma': Inscribed Columns and Civic Religion in Gupta India

Dr Elizabeth Cecil (Leiden)

Date: 14 March 2017

Time: 2:00 PM

Finishes: 14 March 2017

Time: 5:00 PM

Venue: Faber Building, 23/24 Russell Square

Room: F314

The use of inscribed columns by the Gupta rulers and their contemporaries as media for expressions of royal power and prestige is a practice that is well documented, yet poorly understood. Analysis of the textual semantics of the inscriptions has, thus far, dominated the study of the columns, leaving the significance of the visual language and the material semantics of these objects unexplored. Monolithic in form, but certainly not in function, columns were objects with a complex set of social and ritual meanings that extended beyond their particular use as political emblems. Accessing these meanings requires analysis of the contexts in which the objects were viewed and experienced—e.g. the relation of epigraphic texts to the material and visual elements of the columns upon which they were inscribed, the interplay of discrete monuments within the larger built landscape, and the strategic siting of inscribed columns within the wider physical terrain of a polity. This study draws upon recent fieldwork undertaken at key sites of civic religion—Sondhni, Eran, and Mahakuta—where monumental inscribed columns are preserved *in situ*, to outline a new methodology for the study of epigraphic sources in their material contexts. To demonstrate the efficacy of this approach by suggesting new interpretations of these three sites, this presentation will also include contributions by Peter Bisschop and Dániel Balogh.

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April 2017

Philosophy in the Gupta Period

Prof Larry McCrea (Cornell University) and Prof Isabelle Ratié (Université Sorbonne Nouvelle)

Date: 11 April 2017	Time: 2:00 PM
Finishes: 11 April 2017	Time: 5:00 PM
Venue: Paul Webley Wing (Senate House)	Room: S208

Reading and Rationality in Late First Millennium Indian Philosophy

Prof Larry McCrea (Cornell University)

Beginning with the work of the great 7th century scriptural hermeneut and epistemologist Kumārilabhaṭṭa (c. 650 AD), authors of Sanskrit philosophical works of all stripes showed an increasing interest in exploring the presumed pre-knowledge and motivation of potential readers of their works. This led to the gradual emergence of a quite sophisticated theory of the function of a work's "opening sentence" (*ādi-vākya*), specifying with increasing detail the information it must explicitly or implicitly convey if readers are to be effectively motivated to undertake the effort of studying the text in question. Over time, this theory gradually transformed into a more general theory of the rational human agent (*prekṣāpūrvakārin*) and of rationally motivated human action. By the tenth century, this theorization, originally confined to the technical issue of how to properly compose opening sentences, had come to be recognized as a universally applicable model for human action; a model largely shared between the main rival traditions of Indian philosophy during this period.

On the so-called Śabdadhātusamīkṣā, a lost philosophical work ascribed to Bharṭṛhari
Prof Isabelle Ratié (Université Sorbonne Nouvelle)

The fifth-century grammarian-philosopher Bharṭṛhari has long attracted scholarly attention, and deservedly so: his magnum opus, the *Vākyapadīya*, expounds a fascinating doctrine according to which language is the core of all reality, and it had a profound impact on later Indian schools of thought; it was discussed, praised or criticized for centuries in India, in Brahmanical as well as Buddhist circles. The *Vākyapadīya* is not, however, the only grammatical/philosophical work ascribed to Bharṭṛhari in addition to a commentary on the *Mahābhāṣya*: according to several later sources, the same author composed a *Śabdadhātusamīkṣā* or *Ṣaddhātusamīkṣā*. Unfortunately this treatise has not come down to us, and it is still shrouded in much mystery as its main topic, and even title and attribution, are considered uncertain to date. The aim of this talk is to examine allusions to it found in later texts (some of which have not been taken into account by historians so far) and to show that however elliptical, they can provide many important clues about this intriguing work.

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May 2017

Aspects of Royal Ideology in the Buddhist Vinayas
Dr Vincent Tournier (SOAS, University of London)

Date: 9 May 2017 Time: 2:00 PM
Finishes: 9 May 2017 Time: 5:00 PM
Venue: Brunei Gallery Room: B202

Narratives transmitted in the massive, and still largely unexplored Vinaya literature preserved in Indian languages, Chinese, and Tibetan, provide us with a wealth of evidence about the changing self-representation of Buddhist monastics during the Gupta period. This literature shows a clear tendency towards appropriating the values and imaginary of the ruling and the brahmanical classes. Concerns for social hierarchy, purity, and descent are pervasive in the Vinayas, a perfect example being a family of narratives dealing with the royal lineage in which the Buddha Śākyamuni was born. This family of narratives arguably plays a key role in the Buddha's biography, and its legacy may be traced in post-Gupta historiography across Asia. This paper focuses on the blossoming of narratives on the Buddha's royal lineage in India between the 3th and the 5th century CE. Such compositions weaved earlier canonical tropes into a continuous narratives connecting Śākyamuni and his spiritual heirs to the world rulers past and present.

Speaker biography

Dr Vincent Tournier studied History and Anthropology at the University of Strasbourg, and Buddhist Studies at the École Pratique des Hautes Études in Paris, where he obtained his PhD. Before joining SOAS, he worked as a research fellow at the

International Research Institute for Advanced Buddhism (Tokyo), at the International Institute for Asian Studies (Leiden), and as Post-doctoral researcher at the Leiden Institute for Area Studies.

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June 2017

The Sanskritisation of Gandharan Culture
Prof Ingo Strauch (Lausanne)

Date: 13 June 2017	Time: 2:00 PM
Finishes: 13 June 2017	Time: 5:00 PM
Venue: Paul Webley Wing (Senate House)	Room: S208

The manuscripts of Buddhist texts discovered in "Greater Gandhara" bear witness to different phases of the Buddhist culture in this region. The latest texts show traces of a process that represented a paradigmatic shift in numerous cultural areas of South Asia: the abandonment of vernacular Middle Indic idioms in favor of the language of Sanskrit. In "Greater Gandhara" this linguistic shift was accompanied by a gradual transition from the inherited script of this area – the Kharoṣṭhī – to the Brāhmī script that was used in the rest of the Indian subcontinent. This talk will examine the manuscript, epigraphical and numismatic evidence from "Greater Gandhara" and contrast it with data from different South Asian regions. This presentation aims to determine the specific political, social and cultural conditions that characterized the Sanskritisation in the cultural area of "Greater Gandhara."

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July 2017 – No Workshop

August 2017 – No Workshop